

By Edwin Amuga, February 2017

Social Balance and Bernoulli Equation

Introduction

Since the early 20th century, researchers have been interested in the reasons social networks result in two opposing factions worldwide. A dynamic model was recently developed of how and why such a balance might occur. This paper gives a brief introduction to social harmony and a new analysis of the developed model. The comment presented by the article helps one choose the general initial conditions not experienced in systemic analyses. In the research, social networks give rise to four feuding factions as opposed to two. The paper, therefore, characterizes the four factions and sheds light on the size of each. Veerman (2018) looks at the social balance question from a different perspective as compared to the socio-biological peers and concludes that the conglomeration of the two groups narrowly give the majority.

Background

There has been a growing concern about why finite social networks result in two antagonistic factions since the 1940s. Many researchers have approached the problems, including Heider, Harary, and Cartwright, who came up with a formal-graph-theoretical model for social equilibrium inspired by social psychology insights (Goswami, Veena, and Gopisnath Panda 2019). The framework was in harmony with the ideas developed by Heider. The researches proved that a symmetric sign network only balances if as two factions at most. This conclusion by the researchers came to be known as the structure theorem. There has been a disconnect on a dynamic model that demonstrates how and why such a balance occurred until recently when it

was developed. The analysis of Marvel et al. (2011) gave the field a boost after successfully analyzing matrix differential, question dynamics.

$$X' = X^2; X(0) = X_0.$$

The above equation implies that an individual in some way communicates with all individuals $k \in [1, \dots, n]$. If the individual has a positive feeling about an individual or individuals k , then the individual(s) k will most likely influence another individual(s) j in the same direction. Conversely, if an individual, i , has a negative opinion about individual(s) k , their argument is most likely to influence j in the opposite direction to the view of K about j . The equation implies that friends of an individual's friends will most likely become their friends, and the enemies of one's enemies will become one's friend. The enemies of a person's enemies will also become one's friends, and the enemies of one's friends will most likely become one's enemies (Goswami, Veena, and Gopisnath Panda 2019).

Since friendliness cannot be quantified, one can study this problem with the original X_0 value as a random matrix. The researchers assumed an asymmetric matrix X_0 for an adequate analysis of the equation, and the practice was later applied in standard matrices. The study is subdivided into two parts, with the first part being solving the differential equations. The equation is regarded as a particular matrix Riccati equation case, and the solution depends on certain conditions (Goswami, Veena, and Gopisnath Panda 2019). The most critical need that determines the answer is that the X_0 has to have a positive eigenvalue. The major of the real eigenvalues λ should have a geometric and algebraic multiplicity of 1. The second section of the analysis demonstrates that these hypotheses hold in random matrices with a probability of 1 as the element (n) unboundedly grows. The study relies on reasonably delicate points of view on eigenvalues in the case of random matrices.

This paper proposes a more precise and straightforward treatment of the problem. A simple generalization proof of the structure theorem is provided, and network be sign symmetric is abandoned. The equation is treated as a particular Bernoulli equation case rather than as a Riccati equation. In this way, the treatment is simplified and offers the advantage that more can be precisely characterized than non-symmetric and non-normal initial conditions X_0 . A recent random matrices study is used to assert that X_0 has a real, simple, leading and positive eigenvalue with the possibility tending to 1 as the element n tends to infinity.

Consequently, this paper shows that with vast possibility, a random initial condition X_0 neither normal nor symmetric will result in four factions, two of which are comparable to symmetric case factions. The two groups are cohesive, implying that the members of the same factions like the other. The remaining other factions are not since the members do not like each other. If the two cohesive factions combine, they can form a narrow majority. Due to the above developments, a somewhat different framework could be developed for a social balance where the differential equation is substituted by

$$X = XX^T$$

The proposed model brings in two factions that have high possibility under general original circumstances. The examination is this equation is more complicated, and the simplification proposed in the paper is not helpful in the study of the model.

Results

The people living in a society and the attitudes between them define the society. Society is viewed as being in a state of balance if some pressure is applied to change its dynamics (Goswami, Veena, and Gopisnath Panda 2019). A finite network, for instance, with n elements, represents the people in the network, and R represents the associated segments. A metric space Y

with associated metrics are negative and positive. The metrics are scalar quantities such as friendliness quantified on a directed graph G defined on the network V and the set segments R .

There are still two balanced factions that are cohesive. These include each faction that has individuals that like each other. There are also two dispersive factions internally divided so that individuals in either faction dislike each other and even dislike themselves and, as a result, signifies diagonal blocks of negative entries (Veerman, 2018). Each of the dispersive parties have symmetric stance about the other, but the relationship between dispersive and cohesive factions is antisymmetric as they have opposite signs.

1, 2, 3, and 4 are utilized to represent the four factions in the appearance order along the diagonal of the equation. In light of the analysis that x_{ij} corresponds to the opinions of i towards j , it can be speculated that faction two is not liked by group one despite the fact that there still exist optimistic feelings between them and group 1 and these situations might have made them feel at ease and develop negative opinions about themselves. As this goes on, the factions cannot combine with group four because they dislike them. However, there exists common understanding between factions 3 and 4. It is still vague if this is probable to form a sociological point of view. The impossibility raises the question on which possible alliances of two factions will form a majority faction. Symmetrically, eigenvectors v and w are uniformly probable as $-v$ and $-w$. These effects will bring faction 1 and 4 to one side and factions 2 and 3 on the other side. It implies that the cohesive parties 1 and 4 will have the same anticipated amount. Also, the factions will be observed in the same of dispersive factions. If 1 and 2 ally, they will have the same size as the number of positive signs in the vector V . Working with symmetry again, the anticipation is half times of n . Consequently, the factions are likely to create a majority half the time. The equivalent is also accurate for any cohesive and disruptive faction combination.

On the other hand, if the bigger of the two cohesive groups combine with either of the disruptive groups, then it can be expected that they will form the majority. Two cohesive factions have symmetric feelings while cohesive and adhesive are antisymmetric, as in they have opposite sentiment. A combination of entries 1 and 4, and 1 and 3 factions are aimed at finding that which forms the majority. Combining a larger cohesive and cohesive faction creates a majority, and the same is accurate for cohesive and cohesive.

If the differentiation equation $X'(t) = X^2$ is considered and a physical diagram is drawn for the relationship, then the elements X_{ij} are only affected by the particles connected by horizontal and vertical line segments. In a gravitational condition, any particle is attracted by the other particles and has superposition property. The adjacent counterparts cancel out the elements diagonal to the entry X_{ij} entry of $X(t)$.

Works cited

- Goswami, Veena, and Gopinath Panda. "Mixed equilibrium and social joining strategies in Markovian queues with Bernoulli-schedule-controlled vacation and vacation interruption." *Quality Technology & Quantitative Management* 16.5 (2019): 531-559.
- Veerman, J. J. P. "Social Balance and the Bernoulli Equation." *The American Mathematical Monthly* 125.8 (2018): 724-732.
- .